

Supplementary Material D

Shared qpAdm outgroup set:

Mbuti.DG; Han.DG; Chukchi.DG; Karitiana.DG; Papuan.DG; Switzerland_Bichon_Epipaleolithic.SG; Basque.DG; Ju_hoan_North.DG; Iranian.DG; Yoruba.DG

Table D1. qpAdm model outcomes for Jew_Ashkenazi.HO.

Model	Sources	p-value	Feasible
Italian_South + Lebanese + Russian	Italian_South.HO; Lebanese.HO; Russian.DG	0.1445	TRUE
Italian_Central + Lebanese + Russian	Italian_Central.HO; Lebanese.HO; Russian.DG	0.0514	TRUE
Italian_North + Lebanese + Russian	Italian_North.HO; Lebanese.HO; Russian.DG	0.0256	FALSE

Target: Jew_Ashkenazi.HO

p value: 0.0514 | Feasibility: TRUE | [Raw Output](#)

Target: Jew_Ashkenazi.HO

p value: 0.0256 | Feasibility: FALSE | [Raw Output](#)

